

REINTEGRATION OF ADULT MALE OFFENDERS UNDER PROBATION SUPERVISION IN THE PUNJAB, PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

Probation is an essential organ of criminal justice system through which low risk offenders are conditionally released under the supervision of probation officer. The aim of present study is to examine relationship between probation supervision and reintegration of offenders in the Punjab, Pakistan. For this purpose, a sample of 511 probationers as respondents was selected proportionately from 10 districts of Punjab province. The study concluded that the relationship between probation supervision and reintegration of offenders into society was found positive. The offenders arrested in petty offences may be given the opportunity to release on probation rather than putting them behind prison bars. This would reduce prison overcrowding as well as reduce the burden on taxpayers. The probation officers may be equipped with professional knowledge and technical assistance at their offices for the better probation supervision.

Keywords: offenders, probation supervision, probation system, reintegration.

INTRODUCTION

In the Punjab, approximately 103538 people are being controlled by the correctional system of criminal justice; 36295 or 34.97% of these are on probation (National Academy for Prisons Administration, 2024). This makes probation by far the most widely used instrument of the Pakistani correctional system under criminal justice of Pakistan (Khokhar et al., 2019). According to Probation of Offenders Ordinance 1960, probation punishes the convicted offenders without jailing them. Judge orders the convicted person to report a probation officer and the regular meetings between probation officer and the offender are scheduled. Offenders are handed over as probationers to the department of reclamation and probation by judicial magistrates, and judges

of session and high courts who are legally authorized to release conditionally on probation for the period of less than three years. Probationers are supervised and monitored for the purpose of rehabilitation and reintegration into society, and probation system in the Punjab, Pakistan is effective as alternative to imprisonment (Khokhar, 2014; Khokhar et al., 2015; Khokhar et al., 2019). Rehabilitating offenders for reintegration into society, is a basic objective of present correctional system (Butler et al., 2020; Crow, 2001; Garland, 1997). For which, criminal justice system uses a mechanism through its two important organs: prisons as institutionalized correction of offenders; and community-based correction (probation and parole) as de-institutionalized corrective measure

for offenders who remain in the community without having any label of an incarcerated person. Prior studies such as Camp and Gaes (2005), Vieraitis et al. (2007), and Cid (2009) illustrate that the incarceration having criminogenic conditions has strong negative impact on the lives of the people who are imprisoned for any kind of offence. This negative labeling makes the life difficult for ex-prisoner, and most of the time he or she is socially excluded from the members of that community where he or she lives. This social exclusion enhances the chances of recidivism of offenders (Nowak, 2018; Tica & Roth, 2012).

Probation system is more effective in comparison with offender's incarceration in prisons to reduce recidivism. The evidence found by Gendreau and colleagues (2000) that incarceration of offenders resulted in a 7% increase in recidivating compared with community-based sanction. Smith et al. (2002) argued similarly, and Jonson (2010) conducted meta-analysis of 57 studies and reached to the conclusion that custodial sanction was criminogenic and increasing 14% recidivism as compare to noncustodial sanction. Another menace for Pakistani society which has already 165% overcrowded prisons (National Academy for Prisons Administration, 2024) putting burden on tax payers. This is a strong reason that the offenders who have low risk profiles, they are sent to alternative to imprisonment preferably, because they have more chances to be rehabilitated and reintegrated back into society (Lappi-Seppala, 2019; Schmallegger & Smykla, 2012). Pakistani criminal justice system provides the chance to such offenders to avail the option of corrections in the community under probation and parole. From this option, the low-risk offenders do not have any kind of stigma which is necessarily attached with imprisonment (Khokhar et al., 2019).

As Cullen and Gilbert (1982) believe that rehabilitation is a justification of punishment obligating probation system to care the needs of offenders. Philosophy of probation focuses on rehabilitation and the offenders/probationers are regarded as valuable human resource (Brownlee, 1998; Robinson, 2005). Rehabilitation through probation system is a treatment that reduces the inclination of offenders towards criminality in future (Ellsworth, 1996; Schmallegger & Smykla, 2012), as probation system acts in two ways: at first stage, services are provided that stop the offenders from becoming them professional criminals

(Martinson & Wilks, 1977) and at the second stage, probation system helps the offenders in becoming productive and law-abiding citizens of society (McAnany & Fogel, 1984).

According to Encyclopedia of Britannica (2002), probation is vital in due process of justice which begins for adult offenders with pre-sentence investigation. Presentence investigation, in Pakistani context, called social investigation report (SIR) has five major functions. Social investigation report firstly, helps judges in sentencing appropriately; secondly, assists prison management in classifying offenders for correctional programs; thirdly, furnishes information regarding release of criminals on probation; fourthly, aids probation officers in efforts of offenders' rehabilitation during probation supervision; and fifthly, serves for systematic research as an authentic source of information. Furthermore, a pre-sentence investigation evaluates the background of family of an offender, her or her social relationships, occupation, educational status, history of crime committed by him or her, and all the other factors which are pertinent to understand the problem (Devasia & Devasia, 1992; Johnson & Kent, 2019). As per as, release of the offenders is concerned, role of pre-sentence report prepared by probation officer stands significant during trials in courts for decision making. Probation officers are mandated to make systematic planning for rehabilitating and reintegrating probationers through supervision and guidance when they are conditionally released on probation.

Supervision is the fundamental role of probation officer in probation system (Hsieh et al., 2015; Smith et al., 2018; Viglione & Labrecque, 2021). Practice of probation system is based on welfare oriented and non-punitive philosophy of offenders' rehabilitation and their reintegration into society (Brownlee, 1998) as offenders are regarded as human resource and they are managed appropriately (Robinson, 2005). According to Probation of Offenders Ordinance 1960, a probation officer has seven duties. First, a probation officer explains to the probationers placed under his or her charge, the terms as well as conditions of probation order. Second, a probation officer meets the probationers at least once in a fortnight. Third, a probation officer visits the homes of probationers from time to time. Fourth, a probation officer assists the probationers friendly during the process of counseling. Fifth,

probation officer advises the probationers and endeavors to improve their conduct as well as conditions of living. Sixth, a probation officer encourages probationers to make use of recognized agencies for contributing their welfare as well as general well-being. Seventh, a probation officer strives to take advantage of social, educational, and recreational facilities that might be provided by the voluntary agencies (Section, 10).

Rationale of the Study

Although probation system remained under consideration of some researchers in Pakistan from last several years. Aulakh (1986; 2011) argued that probation originated from Islamic history rather than started by John Augustus in 1841 in Boston, United States. Hussain (2009; 2013) investigated the role of probation service in offenders' social reintegration, and its history in Pakistan, particularly in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP). Furthermore, Bhutta (2010) wrote a general overview of probation and parole in Pakistan; Bhutta (2013), Bhutta et al. (2014) assessed risk/need of probationers in Lahore. Adding further in the literature on probation system in criminal justice, Khokhar (2014) explored effectiveness of probation in criminal justice system. In another study, Khokhar and his colleagues (2015) found probation system significantly effective in rehabilitation of probationers.

Bhutta and Wormith (2016) argued that probationers' recidivism was influenced by religiosity which was negatively correlated. Khokhar et al. (2016) analyzed the demographic factors of the offenders concluding that the aged and educated offenders had more chances of rehabilitation as compare to young and uneducated offenders. Khokhar et al. (2019) compared rehabilitation of offenders during imprisonment and probation order, as a result probation system was found significantly effective in offenders' rehabilitation in the Punjab, Pakistan. Similar conclusions were drawn by Khokhar et al. (2023). However, despite all these noteworthy evidence-based contributions in Pakistan, gap is still awaiting to be filled in the area of probation system. The present study is an attempt to contribute to fulfill the gap by scientifically investigating the relationship between probation supervision and reintegration of offenders in the Punjab, Pakistan, and findings are providing an

insight into the probation system would be evidence for policy makers as well as useful in academia for students and researchers. The present study has the following specific objective:

Objective of the Study

- To examine the relationship between probation supervision and reintegration of offenders into society.

Hypotheses

Probation supervision and reintegration of offenders into society has positive relationship. The increase in the level of probation supervision increases the chances of reintegration of offenders into society.

Data and Methods

Population of present research was all offenders who were adult male probationers from the Punjab, Pakistan. Multistage sampling was applied. Ten districts (Bahawalpur, Bhakkar, Faisalabad, Gujrat, Jhelum, Khanewal, Layyah, Mianwali, Sahiwal, and Sheikhpur) out of 36 were selected randomly at first stage as time and cost were the limits. A sample of 511 probationers from ten districts of the Punjab was taken at the second stage by using proportionate sampling. Finally, 10% proportion was fixed to the total ongoing probationers in every district for selection in the study.

A structured questionnaire devised with help of previous literature was used for data collection. Questionnaires were filled in arranged meetings between researcher and respondents, as most of the respondents were illiterate and they were not able to fill in the questionnaires developed in English language. Meetings were arranged by probation officer of district concerned on the request of researcher. The data collected from the respondents was entered into Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS-26) applying statistical tests for analyzing and confirming the relationship among variables.

Data Analysis and Discussion

Data was analyzed by using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS-26). Response variables were interpreted by making simple frequency tables, and chi-square was used to examine relationship between two variables of the study: probation

supervision and reintegration of offenders/probationers.

Probation Supervision

Supervision is the oversight that probation officers exercise over probationers (Cromwell & Del Carmen, 1999; Robinson & Dominey, 2019). Its rehabilitative function includes nurturing of probationers as well as their training. Supervision is conducted with the aim of treatment offenders disciplining and controlling them focused on direction which removes the social barriers and reduces the chances of recidivism. Carrying out a

supervisory process that can accomplish this end is an extraordinarily difficult task. Offenders can be dealt with effectively only on an individual basis and according to their special conditions and needs. Supervision during probation becomes most effective and successful when personal relationship between probation officer and offender (probationer) remains honest and direct (Cromwell & Del Carmen, 1999; Ellsworth, 1990; Schmallegger, 2009; Sieh, 2006). Table 1 depicts the position of probation supervision of the probationers, according to their perception.

Table 1: Probation supervision

Probation Supervision <i>Item scale</i>	<i>f (%)</i>				
	SA	A	U	D	SD
Probation officer discusses the supervision plan with probationers	142 (27.8)	211 (41.4)	48 (9.5)	80 (15.7)	30 (5.6)
Probation officer appreciates the view of probationers regarding supervision plan	162 (31.8)	230 (45.0)	56 (10.9)	40 (7.8)	23 (4.5)
Probation officer considers the needs of probationers seriously	135 (26.3)	241 (47.1)	83 (16.2)	32 (6.3)	30 (5.9)
Probation officer assists the probationers friendly during the process of counseling.	118 (23.1)	187 (36.6)	148 (28.9)	36 (7.1)	22 (4.3)
Probation officer's behavior remains sympathetic during meetings	136 (26.6)	245 (47.9)	60 (11.7)	43 (8.3)	28 (5.5)
Probation officer treats fairly while meeting with probationers	161 (31.5)	223 (43.6)	50 (9.8)	52 (10.2)	25 (4.9)

SA : Strongly Agree A: Agree U :Undecided: D: Disagree SD : Strongly Disagree

Table 1 shows frequency and percentage regarding extent of supervision of a probation officer. According to the information about statement 'probation officer discusses the supervision plan with probationers' 41.4% of the respondents agreed, 9.5% undecided, 15.7% disagreed while 27.8% strongly agreed with the statement, and 5.6% strongly disagreed. And regarding the information about 'probation officer appreciates the view of probationers regarding supervision plan' 45.0% of the respondents agreed, 10.9% undecided, and 7.8% disagreed, 31.8% strongly agreed, and 4.5% strongly disagreed. In response about the statement 'probation officer considers the needs of probationers seriously' 36.3% strongly agreed, 47.1% only agreed, 16.2% 'undecided', 6.3% disagreed and remaining 5.9% strongly agreed.

Responding the statement 'probation officer assists the probationer's friendly during the process of counseling' 36.6% agreed, 28.9% of the respondent undecided, and 7.1% disagreed, whereas 23.1% strongly agreed, and only 4.3% strongly disagreed. According to the information provided in the statement 'probation officer's behavior remains sympathetic during meetings' 26.6% strongly agreed, and 47.9% agreed, 11.7% undecided, while 8.3% disagreed and 5.5% strongly agreed. Regarding the opinion 'probation officer treats fairly while meeting with probationers' 31.5% of the respondents were strongly agreed, while 43.6% agreed, and 9.8% undecided, whereas 10.2% disagreed and only 4.9% strongly disagreed with the opinion.

Reintegration of Offenders into Society

The core objective of probation in criminal justice is to rehabilitate offenders for reintegration into society. And this all is possible only through re-socializing the offender as law abiding citizen as well as opportunities for probationer's available, equal to the other members of family and

community. The offender/probationer has more chances to be rehabilitated if he or she is accepted by the family or community, and not stigmatized for his or her previous criminal behavior. Table 2 presents the information regarding reintegration of offenders (probationers).

Table 2: Reintegration of offenders into society

Reintegration of Offenders <i>Item scale</i>	<i>f (%)</i>				
	SA	A	U	D	SD
Offenders feel reintegrated into society during the period of probation order	179 (34.9)	276 (54.3)	27 (5.9)	21 (3.8)	8 (1.2)
Offenders avail probation period for their rehabilitation	140 (27.5)	297 (58.1)	57 (12.6)	6 (0.9)	11 (0.9)
Offenders' self-esteem remains satisfactory during the period of probation order	114 (22.5)	262 (51.1)	99 (20.2)	19 (3.2)	17 (2.9)
Offenders are not stigmatized by the members of society when they are on probation	89 (17.3)	216 (42.5)	174 (34.9)	23 (4.1)	9 (1.2)
Offenders on probation order avail equal opportunities like other members of society	117 (22.6)	284 (55.7)	67 (13.8)	36 (6.5)	8 (1.2)
Offenders on probation participate in solving the problems faced by their families	185 (36.4)	241 (46.9)	30 (6.5)	39 (7.3)	16 (2.9)

SA: Strongly Agree A: Agree U: Undecided: D: Disagree SD: Strongly Disagree

Table 2 depicts the data in frequency and percentage regarding reintegration of offenders/probationers under probation supervision. With the statement 'Probationers feel reintegrated into society during the period of probation order' 54.3% of the respondents agreed, and 5.9% undecided, while 3.8% disagreed, and 34.9% strongly agreed, and only 1.2% strongly disagreed. And regarding the information about 'Probationers avail probation period for their rehabilitation' 58.1% agreed, and 12.6% undecided, whereas 0.9% disagreed, and 27.5% strongly agreed, 0.9% strongly disagreed. In response of the statement 'Probationers self-esteem remains satisfactory' 22.6% of the respondents strongly agreed, and 51.0% agreed, while 20.2% undecided, and 3.2% disagreed, whereas only 2.9% strongly agreed.

Responding to the statement 'Probationers are is not stigmatized by the members of society, 42.5% agreed, and 34.9% undecided, 4.1% disagreed,

while 17.3% strongly agreed, and 1.2% strongly disagreed. About the statement 'Probationers avail equal opportunities like other productive members of society' 22.6% strongly agreed, and 55.7% agreed, whereas 13.8% undecided, and 6.5% disagreed and 1.5% strongly agreed. In response of statement 'Probationers participate in solving the problems faced by their families' 36.4% strongly agreed, and 46.9% agreed, while 6.5% undecided, and 7.3% disagreed, whereas only 2.9% of the respondents strongly agreed.

Probation Supervision and Reintegration of Offenders

This study proved the hypothesis stating that probation supervision and reintegration of offenders into society has positive relationship. The increase in the level of probation supervision increases the chances of reintegration of offenders into society.

Table 3: Relationship between probation supervision and reintegration of offenders

Probation Supervision	Reintegration of Offenders			Total
	Low	Medium	High	
Good	29	37	47	113

Better	74	84	89	247
Best	40	52	59	151
Total	143	173	195	511

Chi-square value = 1.49 Significance Level: $\alpha = 0.05$ $p < 0.001$

Table 3 shows the empirical data regarding relationship between probation supervision and reintegration of offenders/probationers. The chi-square test was applied to examine the relationship between the variables. According to the data, out of 511 respondents of the study, 195 (38.2%) had high chances of reintegration into society during the period of their probation order under the supervision of a probation officer. And 173 (33.9%) had medium chances whereas 143 (27.9%) had low chances. Furthermore, this table also shows that out of 511 respondents, 151 (29.6%) had best opportunity of supervision to be reintegrated into society. And 247 (48.3%) respondents/probationers had better opportunity, whereas 113 (22.1%) had good opportunity of reintegration under probation supervision. The result of this bivariate analysis indicates that probation supervision has significant and positive relationship with reintegration of offenders/probationers into society. With the increase in betterment of supervision, the chances of reintegration of offenders increase and offenders have higher chances in becoming law abiding citizens.

Conclusion

This quantitative study having sample of 511 probationers from ten districts of the Punjab, Pakistan, examined the relationship between probation supervision and reintegration of offenders. The study concluded that there was significant and positive relationship between probation supervision and the reintegration of offenders in the Punjab, Pakistan. The conclusion of this study has both implications—theoretical and practical. Theoretically, this is the addition in literature produced regarding the understanding of probation system in the Punjab, Pakistan and may be used for academic purpose in the field of criminology and penology, especially in community-based corrections probation. Practically, this may be used in making the policy for improvement of probation system, being a vital component of criminal justice system of Pakistan. As this study proved significant relationship

between probation supervision and reintegration of offenders into society, the low-risk offenders may be released on probation through which the overcrowding in prisons would be reduced that is an impediment in effective prison management and financial burden on taxpayers of Pakistan. Furthermore, supervision skills of probation officers may be modernized through professional trainings and technical assistance may be provided through which they would be able to provide better results in probation supervision.

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